

LICORICE (GLYCYRRHIZA L.) AS MORE THAN A MEDICINAL PLANT: APPLICATIONS, ENVIRONMENTAL CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH IT, AND EFFECTIVE PROPAGATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. This article examines the significance, applications, and cultivation methods of licorice plants (*Glycyrrhiza*) within Uzbekistan. Emphasis is placed on the plant's broad utilization across various industrial sectors, its medicinal efficacy, and its role in national agriculture. Given the decline in natural licorice resources, the article underscores the importance of expanding cultivation, highlights its relevance in land reclamation, and examines its capacity to thrive in saline soils. Additionally, the article provides insights into newly developed propagation techniques tailored for licorice cultivation in Uzbekistan, demonstrating their effectiveness.

Keywords: licorice, sweet licorice, boyan, sweet boyan, smooth licorice, *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L., bitter licorice, *Glycyrrhiza aspera* Pall., Ural licorice, *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* Fisch., liquorice, liquorice root, glycyrrhizin, phreatophyte, meliorant.

There are over 4,300 plant species in our republic, among which 750 species are significant as raw and medicinal resources used in various industries. Licorice, in particular, is notable for its versatile applications across medicine, the food industry, and more than 20 other industrial and agricultural sectors. It ranks first among medicinal plants due to its broad utility, beneficial properties, and minimal adverse effects. [1].

Its natural areas are decreasing due to the high demand for raw licorice materials in the global market. For this reason, on May 16, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued Resolution PR-2970, titled 'On Measures to Increase the Cultivation of Licorice Roots and Their Industrial Processing'. Additionally, on January 27, 2018, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a resolution on the 'Further Development of Licorice and Medicinal Plant Cultivation and Industrial Processing'. These decisions were considered urgent.

In Uzbekistan, three species of the genus *Glycyrrhiza* occur naturally. Among them, smooth licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra* L.) and bitter licorice (*Glycyrrhiza aspera* Pall.) are common, while Ural licorice (*Glycyrrhiza uralensis* Fisch.) is rare within the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Ural licorice (*Glycyrrhiza uralensis* Fisch.). Areas of Ural licorice within the Republic of Uzbekistan include:

Rarely found in the Kongur-Khokiz Mountain Range of Fergana Range at an altitude of 2,210 m above sea level, in the eastern part of the Small Taldyk region, and the Black Uighur River basin.

Found near the villages of Shokhimardon and Aksoy in the Oly Mountain Range, near Yordan village in the Ol Mountain Range, and in Shokhimardon River basin.

Located in the western part of Kolmozor stream headwaters in Boysun district.

Found in West Pamir-Alay, Kashkadarya Valley, at 2,250 m above sea level, 6 km southeast of Guldara village, near the confluence of the Red Water and Qattau rivers.

Located in Parkent Mining and Forestry areas around the Shavezi River and Kalan-soy [2].

Smooth licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra* L.). Smooth licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra* L.) naturally grows along the banks and basins of Amu Darya, Syr Darya, Zarafshan, Chirchik, and other rivers, including their tributaries, once covering large areas. Unfortunately, due to the extensive harvesting of licorice roots by the All-Union “Soyuzlakritsa” Association during the Soviet period, many of these natural areas have diminished or disappeared. As a result, licorice now remains only in small patches in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. In Surkhandarya, Bukhara, Khorezm, Samarkand, Syrdarya, and Tashkent regions, it can still be found in limited areas along the banks of canals, ditches, and drainage channels. These areas cannot be cultivated using mechanization. To prevent *Glycyrrhiza* plants from being included in the “Red Book”, there is an urgent need to strictly protect the species. It is necessary to fully identify the existing areas of sweet licorice for the rational use of its natural resources, conduct cadastral work, assess raw material reserves in current areas, and expand the cultivated areas.

Sweet licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra* L.) and Ural licorice (*Glycyrrhiza uralensis* Fisch.) are the most commonly used plants in medicine, food, and other sectors of the economy. The biologically active substances found in these two plants are similar, and their concentrations are comparable.

The importance of sweet licorice in the national economy is significant, and the use of licorice can be divided into four major areas:

The root is utilized in more than 20 industries, including medicine, food, metallurgy, and others, making it a strong export product.

The flowers are used in beekeeping, while the above-ground parts serve as protein-rich fodder for livestock.

It is a meliorate plant, reducing soil salinity by 2-2.5 times and enriching the soil with nitrogen, humus, and other beneficial elements. It is especially effective in crop rotation with cotton.

Licorice planting plays a role in ecological rehabilitation, helping to stop sand, dust, and landslides.

The roots and rhizomes of the plant contain extractive substances, glycyrrhizin and glycyrrhizin acids, flavonoids (more than 30 types), glycosides, sucrose, cellulose, starch, ascorbic acid, vitamin C, steroids, fatty substance, rubber, protein. In addition, there are macro elements — K, Ca, Mg, Fe, micro elements — Mn, Cu, Zn, Al, Ba, N, Se, Ni, Sr, Pb and other elements. In the surface part, there are protein-protein saponins (steroid tryterpenes), flavones, sugars (monosaccharides, disaccharides), additives, nitrogenous bases, fiber, residual oils, essential oils, organic acids, carotene, chlorophyll and other substances. For this reason, the scope of use of this plant is very wide [3,4].

In medicine. In medicine, the use of licorice dates back to the 4th century BC. At that time, licorice products were highly valued, securing the top position in a competition featuring 233 medicinal plants across 158 complex recipes, held jointly by China, Korea, and Japan. The

multifaceted effects of licorice products on the body, along with their numerous beneficial properties and few negative effects, have been highly appreciated [1].

Preparations such as glyceram, liquiritin, licorice acid, and flavonoids, as well as over 110 other compounds, are derived from licorice. In total, licorice appears in over 1,000 formulations, including tablets, capsules, liquids, pastes, aggregates, and phytoteas.

In modern medicine, preparations made from licorice roots—including dry extracts, dark extracts, and licorice juice—are used to treat colds, tuberculosis, lung diseases, AIDS, and liver, respiratory, and cardiovascular diseases. Additionally, licorice is employed to normalize metabolism and is used for conditions such as gout, eczema, cancer, food poisoning, stomach and duodenal ulcers, inflammations, skin burns, and many other diseases.

In contemporary folk medicine, a decoction of licorice root is used for chest pain, shortness of breath, pulmonary tuberculosis, jaundice, heart disease, colds, snake bites, rabies, bites from rabid dogs, metabolism improvement, dry throat, inflammation of the bladder and gastrointestinal tract, whooping cough, anemia, liver diseases, fever, voice disorders, kidney and bladder inflammation, gum issues, respiratory conditions, and various other ailments. It is also used as a mild laxative, diuretic, and stimulant in cases of chronic constipation.

An anti-inflammatory medication has been developed using saponins and flavonoids extracted from the above-ground parts of licorice, and its effectiveness has been confirmed.

In the food industry, Calorie-free and low-calorie sweeteners, proteins, and other bioactive compounds derived from licorice are among the essential supplementary components used to balance human nutrition on a proper dietary basis. They are particularly beneficial for individuals with diabetes.

From 1 ton of licorice roots and rhizomes, it is possible to obtain 160–200 kg of glycyrrhizin (equivalent to 50 units of sweetness), 100–350 kg of glucose (syrup), 60–90 kg of plant protein, 50–60 kg of vegetable oil, and 100–200 kg of protein feed suitable for livestock. This makes licorice a versatile additive for many food products.

Licorice extract is used in the preparation of kissel (It's a thick, jelly-like beverage), compote, kvass (it's a fermented, mildly alcoholic beverage), sparkling water, and other thirst-quenching beverages, as well as in candies, halva (asian sweeteners), cakes, and various other confectionery products. In Arab countries, a licorice root-based drink, known as "Suss" or "Irksus," is popular and regarded as a traditional beverage. Due to its foaming properties, 1 kg of licorice-based foaming agent is equivalent to 200 kg of egg white in foaming capacity. Additionally, licorice root is used to preserve apples and to enhance the flavor and shelf life of pickled foods such as cabbage, tomatoes, and cucumbers. It is especially valued in Western Europe and the United States for imparting a pleasant flavor in confectionery, non-alcoholic beverages like cola and Bavarian-style kvass, brewing, and in the tobacco industry.

The root extract marketed under the brand name "Otizon" offers a calorie-free sweetness comparable to Acesulfame-K. "Otizon" is used in the preparation of non-alcoholic beverages, confectionery, bakery products, jams, jellies, preserves, food concentrates, chewing gum, toothpaste, and other products. This sweetener can replace 10-50% of sugar, and up to 100% for diabetic-friendly products [3,5].

In the Light Industry: Licorice roots are used to produce a dark yellow dye for coloring wool products, while the above-ground parts yield yellow and red dyes suitable for wool and silk items. Additionally, the roots are used in soap-making and leather processing.

After seed extraction, the remaining pods contain a high concentration of biologically active substances, from which valuable phenolic compounds are extracted. A high-quality blue dye can be derived from the gallic acid in these compounds.

In the Metallurgical Industry: Licorice extract is used as a film-forming agent for coating iron surfaces and in the hydrolysis of non-ferrous metals. In non-ferrous metallurgy, it is also used in electrolysis baths to neutralize acidic sulfur fumes and to precipitate rare metals.

In the Chemical Industry: Licorice is used to fill fire extinguishers, prepare ink and dyes, and to add color to paper.

In the Cosmetics Industry: Licorice is effective in creams, lotions, cleansing solutions, hair products, shampoos, hair dyes, and toothpaste. It is beneficial in skincare as it helps to maintain moisture on the skin's surface.

After the extraction process, the remaining waste materials are used to prepare a mixture that facilitates drilling in the oil industry. In the construction industry, heat- and sound-insulating cardboard, paper-based thermal insulation boards, and regular cardboard and paper are produced. Additionally, the Institute of Microbiology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Akhmedova Z.R.) prepares Microzin-1 and Microzin-2 liquid biofertilizers, as well as dry compost biofertilizers.

Wooden panels for construction can be produced from the plant's stalks, which contain 32-34% cellulose, suitable for producing high-quality paper.

Because the raw material of the licorice is waste-free and has a wide range of applications, it is an exportable product. It is purchased by many countries, including the USA, the UK, the Netherlands, Japan, Germany, Hungary, China, and others.

The uses of the licorice are limitless, with applications in various fields, including agriculture.

In plant cultivation, the products derived from it are of great importance, not only in medicine and the food industry but also in agriculture. A biologically active substance influencing plant growth has been extracted from the licorice. When 1 mg of this substance is mixed with 1 liter of water and applied to seed potatoes before planting, it increases bud germination by 28%. It speeds up the transition from budding to flowering, resulting in a 17% increase in yield and significantly reduces the plant's susceptibility to viral diseases. [4].

The practice of crop rotation offers significant benefits. As a result of crop rotation, both the productivity and quality of the yield improve. Long-term experiments conducted in the Boyovut district of Syrdarya region showed that, due to an increase in the salt content in the soil, fields that were no longer suitable for planting crops (with cotton yields dropping from 7-12 c/ha) were set aside for reclamation. When the method of rotating smooth licorice and cotton was applied, the cotton yield per hectare reached 25-30 c in the first rotation and 30-32 c in the second rotation. In the field where smooth licorice was cultivated, the amount of soluble salts in the soil decreased from 2.0-2.5% to 1.0-1.2% over the first 5 years. The yield of smooth licorice roots and rootstocks from this area was 27 t/ha [6].

Planting sweet licorice alongside other salt-tolerant crops yields good results. In this case, the land is used more efficiently, and additional nutrients are produced. In the conditions of Mirzachul region, the yield of wet mass was 78-490 c/ha from watermelons, 279-840 c/ha from maize, 234-800 c/ha from sorghum, 87-270 c/ha from vigna (*Vigna luteola*), and 95-280 c/ha from dolichos (*Dolichos L.*) when grown alongside licorice [7].

According to observations, when maize was planted in a field where sweet licorice had been cultivated for 4 years, followed by planting cotton (without treatment to speed up germination), the cotton germination rate was 52.5%.

In contrast, when cotton was planted in a field without sweet licorice, the germination rate ranged from 6-15%. When cotton was planted instead of licorice, it grew well, developed successfully, and had higher yields. The quality of cotton fibers (strength, length) also improved [8].

In livestock farming, this plant contains protein, fats, carbohydrates, and sugars in its above-ground parts, which are 1.5-2.0 times higher compared to alfalfa and esparcet (sainfoin). Naturally growing licorice contains 11-18% of protein, 10-15% of nitrogen protein, 3-9% of fats, and 6000-20000 IU/kg of phytoestrogens in its above-ground parts. When cultivated, these indicators improve, with the plant containing 8.2-24.0% of protein, 10.5-19.7% of protein, 3.2-9.1% fats, and other substances.

Additionally, 11 beneficial compounds have been identified, including oxalic acid, tartaric acid, citric acid, malic acid, amber acid, and fumaric acid. Free amino acid content accounts for 4.6-6.0%, while phenolic compound content is 1.5-2.8% [5].

The above-ground parts of licorice are used as silage, hay, and flour for livestock. The Botany Institute of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan has developed a technology for preparing silage from the above-ground parts of licorice for livestock. Its nutritional properties are highly rated for livestock.

Licorice contains biologically active substances that regulate metabolic processes and play a significant role as a source of phytoestrogens. These substances are particularly valuable because they have a stimulating effect on animals whose hormonal activity has decreased. Licorice has fattening and energizing properties and can increase the fat content of cow's milk by 1-1.2%.

In our experiments, it was proven that, in the second year of licorice cultivation, 70-100 c/ha of nutritious hay was harvested, and from the third year onward, more than 220-300 centners per hectare were obtained.

The smooth sweet licorice fields used as pasture.

In beekeeping. Sweet honey can be obtained from the flowers of licorice. At least 45 kg of nectar can be obtained from 1 hectare at one time. Nectar extraction can be repeated many times. Licorice flowers are mainly pollinated by insects, especially bees, which are of great benefit in pollinating flowers and have an important role in increasing plant seed yield.

Smooth licorice stalks cut from the water's edge for hay.

The sweet licorices in full bloom

Meliorative Properties and Efficiency

Plants that are highly resistant to salinity are relatively rare. One such plant is smooth licorice, which is also considered a potent salinity-modifying species. During its vegetation period, smooth licorice develops salt-tolerant symbiotic bacteria in its roots, enriching the soil with nitrogen, humus, and other beneficial compounds. It increases soil fertility and reduces salinity by 2.0–2.5 times (dry residue) over a 4–5 year period. In scientific experiments, smooth licorice was grown in soils containing salt concentrations (dry residue) of 2.5–3.0%, with up to 1.5% sulfate and 0.3% chloride salts, and scientific observations were conducted [6, 9]. The results indicated that as the salt concentration (dry residue) in the soil exceeded 2.0%, the survival rate of planted cuttings and seedlings decreased. In the areas where smooth licorice was planted, an increase in soil salinity was observed during the first years. From the third year onward, the most intense meliorative activity began, and by the end of the fifth year, nearly 80–85% of the soil salinity was neutralized [8, 10].

In the second year of its growth, smooth licorice roots reach the groundwater and evaporate water through the plant's aerial vegetative organs, which helps to reduce soil salinity. In one vegetation period, it can evaporate 20–25 thousand tons of water per hectare. As a result, the groundwater level in areas where the plant's roots reach decreases by more than 1 meter compared

to other areas. The plant has thick, small leaves, and in the summer, the lower leaves of the stem fall to the ground, covering the soil surface. Additionally, the growing stems and branches shade the soil surface, increasing the relative humidity of the air by 16–20% and reducing the temperature by 8–11°C. This also slows the wind speed on the soil surface by 1.5–2.0 times. These ecological changes result in a reduction of evaporation from the soil surface, the primary cause of salinization, by 2–3 times. As a result, in soils at a depth of 1.5 meters, where soluble salts in dry residue are 2.0–2.5%, with chloride anions at 0.1–0.2% and sulfates at 1.0–1.5%, after 5 years of smooth licorice cultivation, the salt content in the soil decreased to 0.8–1.0%; 0.03–0.05%; and 0.6–0.8%, respectively, or even lower values were observed [6, 11].

Status in the fall of the first year

Status in the fall of the third year

The condition at the end of the fifth year of vegetation

Smooth licorice is a phreatophyte plant capable of penetrating gypsum layers in the soil with its roots. Due to its rapid root growth, it reaches the groundwater, making it suitable for cultivation in saline soils where brackish water is present near the surface. For this reason, it is an invaluable plant for preventing soil erosion, sand movement, and salt spread, as well as for creating new pastures for livestock. According to research by Madaminov, it was found that from the third year onward, sand movement stopped in areas where smooth licorice was planted. In untreated areas, however, 38.8 tons or 25 m³ of sand moved per hectare in the second year. For this reason, A. Kuzinev developed a method for planting smooth licorice in saline soils with natural moisture [12, 13, 14].

A smooth licorice field cultivated for five years produces 12–14 tons of roots and rhizomes, as well as 70–80 tons of hay per hectare.

Another beneficial property of smooth licorice, identified in our experiments, is its ability to accumulate glycyrrhizin acid in soils with chloride-sulfate salts, as opposed to non-saline gray

soils. For example, in our experiments, seedlings of smooth licorice, grown from the same seed in identical ecological conditions, were transplanted into two different environments. The licorice plants grown in Tashkent conditions accumulated 9-9.5% glycyrrhizin acid in their roots and rhizomes, while those grown in the chloride-sulfate saline soils of Mirzachul accumulated 11.5-12% glycyrrhizin acid in their roots and rhizomes [10].

The period of full ripening of smooth licorice seeds

As the demand for plant root raw materials increases, the yield and quality indicators of smooth licorice roots are frequently harvested before reaching the desired levels. In the fields where harvesting occurs, the necessary agronomic measures are not sufficiently carried out. As a result, the area of these fields has diminished. In the lower reaches of Amu Darya River in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, natural licorice fields covered 18,000 hectares in 1965, and their root yield in the reserves amounted to 59,354 tons. By 2020, the total area of licorice fields had decreased to 6,369.5 hectares, with an average yield of 5.58 tons per hectare [15, 16].

It is essential to increase the production of this valuable raw material, which is widely used in various sectors of the national economy. Therefore, the preservation, restoration, improvement of yields, and enhancement of the quality of natural sweet licorice fields must be intensified.

For this, it is necessary to consistently implement developed technologies, further develop new ones, and apply them in practice.

To increase the yield and restore natural smooth licorice fields, optimal conditions must be created. This can only be achieved through the comprehensive implementation of melioration measures, fully considering soil and climatic conditions. The yield and quality of licorice roots largely depend on agronomic measures such as soil type, root density, and timely irrigation.

When processing natural smooth licorice fields (especially when harvesting perennial plants, opening irrigation furrows, and filling sparse areas with plantings), quality work must be carried out.

Efforts to increase smooth licorice through planting began in the mid-19th century in Australia, England, Germany, Italy, and France, and by the end of the century, Russia and later Azerbaijan joined the efforts. By the mid-20th century, extensive scientific research on this field had been conducted in Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Moldova, and other countries. However, efforts to increase yields through planting have been ineffective. Up until that time, planting was recommended using root cuttings and seeds. The ineffectiveness of these efforts was connected to the shortcomings of the planting methods that were recommended at that time.

When planting with root cuttings, more than 2.5-3.0 tons of root cuttings are required per hectare, and it is difficult to find enough planting material for large areas. Specifically, a smooth

licorice field yielding 14 tons per hectare over 4–5 years can provide enough planting material for only 2.4 hectares. For 100 hectares, more than 300 tons of root cuttings are needed, and this material must be collected from more than 43 hectares of licorice fields. If more than 52% of the harvested total consists of root cuttings, then a larger area will need to be harvested. Collecting this much planting material from large areas is quite difficult and costly.

For this reason, the expansion of smooth licorice cultivation has remained a challenging and significant issue to this day.

To partially address these problems, special scientific studies were conducted between 1991 and 2000, leading to the development of a new method for propagation — growing seedlings from smooth licorice seeds and transplanting the seedlings to produce raw material. This method has been proven to be more effective than previous methods in many aspects. In this field, A.D. Kuzinev defended his PhD dissertation titled "The Bioecological Foundations of Growing and Propagating Smooth licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra* L.) from Seed."

The first and third patents for propagating smooth licorice were granted to scientists from the Botanical Institute of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan (under the scientific supervision of A.D. Kuzinev and O.A. Ashurmetov) in 1996 and 2006, respectively. The second patent, granted in 1998, was awarded to Russian scientists [13, 17].

Currently, three methods are used for establishing smooth licorice cultivation areas:

Direct sowing of seeds,

Planting from root cuttings, and

Growing seedlings from seeds in small areas and then transplanting the seedlings.

In the new method of growing seedlings from seeds, it is possible to obtain enough seedlings to transplant into 60–70 or even 100 hectares of land in one vegetation period. In this method, seedlings can be grown in a heated room at any time of the year. The seedlings grown can be transplanted into any soil conditions [14].

When propagating from root cuttings, 3.0 tons of root cuttings are needed to plant 1 hectare, and this amount of raw material is obtained from a 4,286 m² smooth licorice field grown for 4–5 years. Using the new seedling method, enough seedlings for planting 1 hectare can be grown in just 143 m² in one year.

The highest survival rate of cuttings is 65-70%, while seedlings have a survival rate of 85-95%.

The new method offers strong plant viability, and it is possible to grow the plants even in highly saline, shallow groundwater areas, with natural moisture (without irrigation). This is a new direction developed by us [12].

When growing smooth licorice from seedlings in saline, unprofitable areas, 14 tons (dry) of root product can be harvested from 1 hectare after 5 years of growth. In this case, \$2,200 is spent, and \$4,800 in net profit is obtained [assuming the price of 1 ton of roots is \$500 (in the global market, 1 ton of roots is valued between \$500—1100), this would amount to \$7,000]. Additionally, 70–80 tons of dry product (hay) can be harvested from the above-ground part. If no other crops are planned for planting in the area after harvesting the root yield, smooth licorice can be replanted without sowing, and through the necessary agronomic measures, the field can be restored. The above-ground yield can be harvested annually, and the underground yield can be collected again after 5 years.

When growing seedlings, 1 hectare can be planted with seeds at a cost of \$7,124.35, which will yield enough seedlings for planting 50 hectares.

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